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THE ROLE OF SPEECH IN THE FORMATION OF SCIENTIFIC LANGUAGE AND MEDICAL TERMS

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ABSTRACT: In a world of rapidly evolving scientific concepts and terminology, word terminology plays a leading role. The modern information system is characterized by the rapid growth of language communication. The growing activity of translation, the growing share of bilingualism in modern society, and the great achievements of science and technology have led to the emergence of not only new names, but also entire semantic fields. At the same time, the process of speech acquisition is accelerating, primarily reflecting the trends of globalization in the language of science.

Keywords: language, vocabulary, medical terms, speech, science.

INTRODUCTION

The process of acquiring a phrase in a foreign language is more or less specific to any language at all stages of development, because languages do not exist in isolation. Learning to borrow in a language has a long tradition in foreign and local linguistics. At the end of the 19th century, Baudouin de Courtenay, after studying this subject, came to the conclusion that the phenomenon of speech really existed in all layers of language: we can see that there is no language "[Baudouin de Courtenay 1963: 363].

A.A. Reformatsky wrote: "There is no single language on earth whose vocabulary is limited to its own words. In every language there are words, that is, words in a foreign language. In different languages and at different stages of their development, these" non-native "words share is different" [Reformed 2004: 139].

The problem of speech in Russian and foreign linguistics has always been in the center of attention and a lot of research has been devoted to it. I.A. Bo- duen de Kurtene, G. Shuxardt, L.B shcherba, A.A. Potebnya, A.A. Reformatskiy, V.V. Vinogradov, Yu.S. Sorokin, O.S. Axmanova, L.P. Krysin, Ferdinand de Saussure, E. Xaugen, U. Vaynrayx, M.A. Breiter, Ye.V. Rosen et al. Worked on this problem. It should be noted that in the past, the approach to the study of speech was one-sided and formal: researchers were mainly interested in the sources and dates of speech, and most importantly, the historical causes and conditions of speech.

MAIN PART

In the twentieth century, linguists focus not only on the source of words, but also on grammar, vocabulary, phonetics, spelling, their mechanisms of assimilation in a foreign language, changes in its semantics, and the relationship with the lexical units of the host language. The ways in which words move from language to language can be both direct and indirect, and the task of linguistics is to define and describe them linguistically correctly.

In lexicology, the concept of "word acquisition" combines many different lexical phenomena:

1. Barbarisms - foreign words and phrases used in a language that is accepted without translation, according to the graphics and spelling of the source language. For example, in Russian "tet-a-tet" and "tete-a-tete", "alter ego"., You can find words like "adieu". Examples of English translations from French include: bon mat, chic, and more. [Galperin 1958: 71].

2. Internationalisms - can be divided into two types:

- similar to the origin or historical development of words belonging to the general etymological fund of a number of languages, for example: Russian. civilization, English. civilization, German. Civilization, French. civilization, Spanish. Civilization, rus. culture, English. culture, German. Culture, French. culture, Spanish. culture; rus. philosophy, English. philosophy, German. Philosophie, French. philosophie, ispan.filosogia and others;

-international words derived from the language of the people who created or shared objects identified by most of the world's languages, for example: English sport, russ. sport, nemis. Sports, French. sport, russ. satellite, ingl. satellite, German. Sputnik, French spoutnik and others.

3. Exotisms are words that express the truths of national cultures that are borrowed from a foreign language, have no clear equivalents, and are characterized by incomplete assimilation. The peculiarity of exoticisms is the uncertainty for the host language, as well as the instability of the external form and the low activity of word formation. From the various languages of the world available in modern Russian, the following words can be cited: vendetta, nandu, karan, radja, rahat-lukum, chalma, chachvan, sherif, and others. A similar phenomenon is observed in English, for example: bohemia, harakiri, karaoke, kungfu, perestroika, tsar, kiosk, prose, intifada, gonzo, etc., and other words in European languages Among foreign linguists, a group of "Global Linguists" analyzes the relationship between English and other languages. Such researchers are distinguished not by the factors that lead to or contribute to

speech, but by their attempts to understand the processes and structures of world linguistics. One of the most interesting in this regard is the theory of concentric circles by B. B. Kachru, which allows us to assess the degree to which the English language system penetrates into the systems of many languages of the world (including Russian). The reason for this phenomenon is linguistic globalization:

- 1) blurs the boundaries between languages;
- 2) eliminates "regionalization", resulting in post-standard languages;
- 3) the evaluator contributes to the disappearance of words that do not have meaning;
- 4) opens up new possibilities for language games: for example, word games, allusions, stylistic games.

Thus, borrowing from other languages is a natural process that characterizes every developed national literary language and language of science.

Let's take a closer look at the formation of the language of science, especially medicine.

Late thirteenth-early twelfth-century England provides an interesting example of the language of struggle, literature, and science for English as the basis of the national literary language. The creation of new scientific terms depended mainly on words derived from Latin as well as Greek. According to Ya. Vityukhovskaya, the peculiarities of Latin words of this period were that they entered not through oral means, but through books. Among them were many verbs and adjectives: operate, cultivate, demonstrate, complete, accept, affect, locate, separate, senior, junior, minor, inferior, exterior, superior, dependent, [Ya.Vityukhovskaya 2000: 27].

The most important features of the words Loti-Romanticism are: the predominance of two-syllable and polysyllabic bases with prefixes, prefixes ending in a consonant: ab-, ad-, corn-, dis-, ex-, in-, im-, il -, sub-; hesitation of consonants: bb, cc, ft, ll, mm, nn, pp, rr, ss, tt. It should be noted that most of the Latin elements were indirectly transferred from French to modern English. Greek words and word-forming elements, like Latin, are mainly international and are widely used in the scientific terminology of many languages.

CONCLUSION

In the 15th and 16th centuries, in addition to words derived from classical languages, there were also words derived mainly from Italian, Spanish, and Dutch. A few words from these languages indicate cultural and trade ties with these countries.

In the 19th century, English also included words derived from French, mainly technical terms: parachute, chassis, chauffeur, faselage, and so on. Adjuvant (adjuvant), bandage (bandage), massage in medical terminology (massage), accoucheur (obstetrician), tourniquet (tow) and others. [Ya.Vityukhovskaya 2000: 29].

The history of the development of the language of science on the basis of the Russian language also traces a number of directions derived from the German (18th century), French (19th century), and English (20th century) languages. The basis of the leading lexical and semantic processes in the Russian language of the 18th century, especially the first third, was profound social changes, the essence of which was the extraordinary expansion of international relations, the transformation of the entire Western way of life. In language, these processes are primarily concerned with the development of lexical content, mainly words, concepts, events, words related to social, state names, in the broadest sense, fields, as well as specific scientific disciplines, including medicine.

If earlier (until the twentieth century) the development of science and, accordingly, the formation of scientific terminology in Russian was much later than in Western countries, now the development of science in Russia and other developed countries, the simultaneous emergence of the same scientific disciplines in different countries (space research, ocean, environment) - environment, etc.) is growing at a high level. Scientific contacts of scientists from different countries are expanding, joint development of certain scientific problems is carried out, which requires the approximation of relevant terminology, reference to the international language - English or the International National Language Foundation.

The modern period of the development of the language of science in different languages is characterized by an increase in the use of terms from other languages, mainly English. Speeches are, as a rule, not translated, but adapted to the target language. In particular, many words derived from English are found in the economic, computer, and medical terminology of various languages. For example:

- indicator (russ.indikator, nem.Indikator, frants.indicateur),
- marker (russ.marker, nem. Marker, frants.marqueur),
- monitoring (russ.monitoring, nem. Monitoring, frants. Monitoring),
- stimulator (russ.stimulator, nem. Stimulator, frants.stimulateur),
- screening (russ.skrining, nem. Screening, frants. Screening).

The above examples show that in the 21st century, science, especially the language of medicine, is moving towards globalization. As English is a widely recognized international language, it has the greatest influence on the formation of modern industrial terminology in various national languages.

Medical terms based on elements of the Greek-Latin language are also easily internationalized, for example:

- russ. lipoma, angl. lipoma, nem. Lipoma, frants. lipome;
- russ. fibroma, angl. fibroma, nem. Fibroma, frants. Fibrome

An increase in the amount of word acquisition leads to a state of terminological system in which terminological synonymy increases sharply (including due to the presence of vocabulary), which impedes adequate comprehension of scientific information, accurate translation of scientific medical literature, mutual understanding and mutual enrichment of national medical schools. and the regulation of the terminological system.

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